

Weekly Progress Report

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Introduction:

This brief report summarizes the assignment performed by RC3 students, which was to troubleshoot the 10 m node due to the following problem:

The supply voltage of 10m node was critically low for an unknown reason.

Plan:

1. To see if there was any loose cable or anything that looks suspicious.
2. To check if capacitor was disconnected.
3. To connect RS-mote to the computer via USB-TTL cable
4. To use ss command to print out the system summary of the mote and back it up
5. To use the re command to print out the report mask or the mote and back it up
6. To upgrade the firmware using avrdude to version 6.9
7. To reset the report mask
8. To disconnect the FTDI cable and reboot

Activities:

First Troubleshooting (28/08)

- We started by looking for any loose connections and we did not find any.
- Then we measured the voltages from the solar panels. The results were 15V on each. The outputs from the respective capacitors were 3.6V and 2.2V
- We printed the system summary and made a copy of the report mask
- In the process of re-flashing the firmware, we got the node into an erroneous state. The node's RED LED would go on and remain on. The point to note here is that we used avrdude on windows and did not include the verification state after writing the hex file.
- We isolated the solar panels and ended the session, noting that the "faulty" capacitor voltage had now increased to 2.9V

Second Troubleshooting

- With Robert's help, on Aug 31, we managed to re-flash the node and re-connected all sensors at the voltage after this session was 2.92V.
- We observed a steady decline in this voltage and on Sep 1, the node stopped transmission completely with $V_{MCU} = 2.35V$
- On Sep 2, we changed the power source of the node to the other capacitor (A as shown in the figure).

- Initially this was not straightforward because the capacitors are connected in series. The voltage at the terminal of A (circled in white) was over 5V.
- We decided to change the GND of the mote to point B1 and the V+ to point A1 (see image below) to get just the 3.6V across capacitor A.

- We restored the full reports and the node started to run again seamlessly.